

STRUGGLE FOR SELFHOOD IN THE STORY “RUNAWAY” BY ALICE MUNRO

Ibodova Maknuna Bahodirovna

Independent Researcher

Annotation: In the whole world, the gender of feminine is regarded as the originator of every human being but she never gets a respectable status from her opposite gender. A sense of inferiority always remained prevalent on the personality of a woman. The quest of woman for identity and their struggle for selfhood is portrait through Alice Munro’s works. Though Munro never considered her a feminist writer but her writings and works clearly states her feminism in the roles of the novels. Because of the unique writing style and themes, her short stories are considered as the novels or novellas. The stories she wrote aftermath were based on her own life and the loneliness of aged people.

Key words: feminism, feminist writer, identity, self-discovery, escapism, male dominant society.

Alice Munro kept the mentality throughout her life that women is always remained an object to the man. She faced the same difficulty in her characters especially in the women to explain the degradation in the society. Her efforts for the self-discovery of the women could be discovered in her works. She gave her female characters an essence of male powers. The beings of her novels specifically females grow from the soil to the sky. She excellently wrote about the women sufferings in the male dominant society.

The titles of her stories are very centric to the plots. “Runway” is the perfect example of it. The story starts not with the escapism but with the returning to the home. Carla heard the car coming before it topped the little rise in the road that around here they called a hill. It’s her, she thought Mrs. Jamieson-Sylvia-home from her holiday in Greece.

In her story, Munro explained the struggle of a woman who is suppressed by her husband, her daily household chores and is disturbed by the mind-set of her neighbors. She tried the method of escapism which is not fruitful. The use of fence is very much important in these stories. Fence in the house is predicted as the shackles of the woman in which she is surrounded. “Runaway” story propagates two main themes: one is the quest of the woman’s identity and secondly the burden of family and relations either with children or neighbors. “Runaway” is story which just increases the burden of the difficulties in the voyage which is somewhat easy and comprehensive.

In “Runaway” story three different runaways are shown first one is about Carla who wants to get away from bad relationship. Second is about the neighbor Sylvia and third is about the white Goat. There is noteworthy cover in the utilization of the expressions “female journey” and “female mission” in the writings talked about in this article, and both are utilized as other options to the customary, manly mission. As history repeats itself, after few years same thing happens in these three Runaways repeats. The arrival might be better comprehended not as a disappointment, but rather as the purpose of fruitful consummation of the story design get under way. In “Runaway” stories Journey of Carla is balanced and it slows down in the beginning. It is like three towns far from home and feels like hazards from life. She first runs from her home and after some time she realizes and came back.

In correlation, the sudden abbreviation of Carla's adventure proposes a quintessential disappointment of will, a disappointment intensely underlined with the setting in “Runaway”. The story of gathering of departures and the unmistakable and unexpected motioning of the account to chivalrous mission theme and Heroic motif.

The main characters of Munro’s stories are basically not more than a puppet that is completing their responsibility in the story and in the journey of their life in the story. Many critics assumed that Munro’s characters have choice either to go with the journey or to protest it. One can also look upon the character of Salvia as a person who has lost her identity in long go. She wanted other to be charge of her life and to fulfill this she chose Carla. On the other hand, Clark, husband of Salvia believed that

she gone insane because she was living with him. Critic Campbell believed that Clark is playing a vital role in this journey he is same as that old man one meet during journey who tells tales of beasts and help passenger pass their time but have no other significance when the journey finishes [1., p. 56]. Salvia mostly tried to provide Carla with money and clothes and make sure that she does her work properly. Munro in the later part of the story depicted Salvia as positive side or as light with her silver blonde hair and her being in the warmth of Greece and on other hand Clark is represented as hazard with the dark hair.

Like other character Flora the goat who in term of relationship is out of bounding with other characters but have similar tendency to get away. Carla always fantasies about many things in one of the incident she has seen Flora the goat flying. She depicts the incident that Flora climbed on fence like an eel and vanished into thin air. These all illusion are the symbols as the inner desire to run away.

In many forms of life, the quest of women's is still bound up with males. Many critics portray the custom as established in the conviction “in this new land, unencumbered by history and social mishap, a man will have the capacity to accomplish finish self-definition”. Defeating ladylike traps is a urgent part of this manly account of self-revelation. As progressively “Clark's mind-set weighted down all their inside space” [2., p. 9], Carla retreat to incrementally far off peripheries of the claustrophobic residential focus that Clark speaks to. All the females want to escape from home to live their lives and they wants to escape from the male dominated world where they all were fighting for their identities.

In “Runaway” story Carla's escape is breakdown by her fear from the society and she have a fear of running away from her home. As she run away from her home her fear increases. Her fear is described in the story that she started to cry quietly, she also begun to shake, she was badly. In the other story character named Carla calls Cark: “Come and get me. If it's not too much trouble Come and get me” [4., p. 267].

“Runaway” depicts that Carla comes back home without her victory because she is unable to escape from her home and come back again to her home. Some critics describe that female's quest for their identity requires an option. Franzen, one of the

famous critics explain that “women’s battle to pick up regard, fairness, and flexibility in the public arena” – what's more, an otherworldly mission: “a lady's enlivening to the profundities of her spirit and her position in the universe” [3., 98]. These two undertakings, she contends, are not elite, in any case, bolster and advance each other. As indicated by Franzen’s contention, ladies’ missions are transformative and informative.

In “Runaway”, “she had utilized the word ‘bona fide’. I have felt the need of a more valid sort of life” [2., p. 33]. However, this idea of “legitimacy” is attached with a conventional setup. Furthermore, individualistic confidence in the true self that Carla can't manage. After leaving Clark, she reviews that how she considered him to be the engineer of the life in front of them, herself as hostage, her accommodation as both legitimate and choice. At the point when Carla wants to takeoff from Clark, then it is stated that he runs away by her. In “Runaway” every female traveler comes back without victory because they all are unable to run away from their homes. By this Munro shows that their life is bounded within the four walls of the house. Their destiny is only related with the household things and she explains that these women are bounded in all these activities throughout their lives and this leads to stay deficient in their life.

References:

1. Campbell, Joseph *The Mythic Dimension: Selected Essays (1959–1987)*. Editor Anthony Van Couvering. 1993.
2. Dakin, Kymberly, “Runaway” by Alice Munro, indiebound.org, 26 Oct 2009. Web .16 April 2009.
3. Franzen, Jonathan. “Introduction: Runaway.” Alice Munro. London: Vintage, 2006.
4. Munro, Alice. “Chance”, “Soon”, “Silence”, “Runaway”. London: Vintage Books, 2006.